

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹				
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance
Municipality			x		
Decision makers				x	
Officers/technicians			x	x	x
Researchers	x	x	x	x	
General Public				x	
xxx					

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	FE_PV
Name	Identification of Photovoltaic potential on the roofs and public areas
Description	Identification of Photovoltaic potential on the roofs considering exposure and urbanistic limitations
Primary User	Municipality/ citizens / professionals
Goal	Identification of rooftops where installing PV panels firstly by exposure (maximising solar radiation), and, subsequently by limiting surface to respect urbanistic regulation would be more effective.
Owner	Deda - FBK
Status	Completed
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	Ferrara is located in the Po Valley (Pianura Padana), one of the most polluted areas in Europe. The high pollution level is a result of a concentration of most of the industrial activities in Northern Italy in combination with the orographic and meteo-climatic conditions of the Po

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

	<p><i>River basin. As a consequence, Ferrara deals with high pollution levels and deteriorated air quality.</i></p>
<p>Strategy/Plan/Regulation</p>	<p><i>The transition to green energy refers to different policy tools at the local and regional level.</i></p> <p><i>Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP)</i> <i>is the main strategy driving mitigation actions in Ferrara. Two specific objectives were identified as relevant for this use case:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>MGS14: employment of energy efficiency requirements in urban plans and restoration plans (mitigation action).</i> <p><i>To support energy-sustainable interventions and the restoration of specific areas, energy efficiency requirements will be applied to building envelopes, installation of renewable energy systems and consumption control tools. This use case can support the implementation and monitoring of this action using accessible visual tools.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>MGS26: promotion of renewable energy sources through photovoltaic energy – 2030 target (mitigation action).</i> <p><i>This action targets the construction of new photovoltaic solar renewable energy systems for the period 2021-2030 using public-private partnerships. The use case can support this action by providing accurate information on highly suitable areas for PV installation and publishing estimates of future power generation levels. Based on this data, target-specific incentives can be devised and managed.</i></p> <p><i>PAIR2030 (Integrated Regional Air Quality Plan)</i> <i>is an action plan prepared by the Emilia-Romagna region through which it defines the air quality policies in a holistic manner. PAIR2030 identifies the measures to be implemented in the sectoral and urban areas that have an impact on air quality, in order to orient them towards the common goal of reducing atmospheric emissions and thus protecting health. The promotion of renewable energy sources as a source of energy and thermal consumption is directed especially to new buildings (C5 action area).</i></p> <p><i>Guidelines on installing thermal insulation, solar, and photovoltaic panels on buildings.</i></p> <p>https://www.comune.ferrara.it/it/b/25746/linee-guida-per-interventi-di-efficienzamento-energetico</p> <p><i>The Guidelines for energy efficiency interventions, approved by resolution of the City Council No. 2023/113, extend the possibility of installing photovoltaic panels on previously excluded buildings such as historical buildings under certain conditions and regulate the installation rules for these buildings. The output of this use case can support the implementation of local regulations and lead to changes in urban construction regulations.</i></p>

<p>Local Green Deal / City contract(s)</p>	<p>The General Urban Plan (PUG) is the main urban planning tool of the municipality that outlines the key strategic choices of urban planning and development with reference to its entire territory. One action line specifically is important for this use case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Objective 1 > Strategic Line 6> Project Action 3. <p>The action aims to develop various interventions to support photovoltaic energy production on roofs and walls of public and private buildings, with particular reference to industrial buildings, while ensuring the preservation of architectural quality.</p>
<p>European Green Deal Policy Area</p>	<p>The EU aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050, which requires the decarbonisation of various domains of human activity including mobility, housing, agriculture, and infrastructure. The energy system powering these activities needs a radical transformation by reducing the energy demands on one side and accelerating the deployment of renewable sources of energy on the other. The adoption of the Climate Law puts high priority on the clean energy transition and renewable energy deployment to replace fossil fuels. To accelerate the rollout of renewable energy, the 2023 revised Renewable Energy Directive was adopted, which facilitates permitting procedures. The Directive recognizes renewable energy as an overriding public interest, allowing Member States to establish dedicated accelerating zones in areas with high renewables potential and low environmental risk, featuring short and simple permitting processes.</p>
<p>Precondition</p>	
<p>Data requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital surface model (DSM) - LINKE turbidity (LT) maps to approximate the solar radiation under clear skies - Existing photovoltaic panels layer - Building footprints with height value - List of parking lots - List of urbanistic limitations - Road graph <p>Tools and algorithm:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FBK: PV Potential algorithm (Solar potential estimation) - FBK: Roof Pitches Segmentation - FBK: roof - road proximity algorithm - FBK: Solar and photovoltaic panels segmentation 	
<p>Postcondition</p>	

<p>DRI (Decision Ready Information)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total radiation over Ferrara. Raster of solar radiation (monthly) (https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/601806dd-3e61-40b4-8d47-6fec2e9addbe) - Segmented roofs solar potential. Average potential (KWH) for each suitable roof pitch. Polygon layer with a KWH field that expresses the theoretical roof pitches and public areas potential generated by photovoltaic panels. (https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/4607d7fd-611a-4cb5-990f-e3215e5f7f3f). - - Parking lot irradiation. Vector public parking lot layer with the estimated value of the potential annual radiation in kWh-m2-year (https://dati.comune.fe.it/dataset/potenziale-solare-parcheggi)
<p>Use of DRI</p>	<p><i>Useful dataset for the Identification of suitable roofs and parking areas for photovoltaic panels installation.</i></p> <p><i>This DRI could be useful to understand, in the future, if the guidelines for photovoltaic installation should be changed (e.g. simplifying the constraints)</i></p>
<p>Use case processing steps</p>	
<p>FE-PV_BPMN.drawio</p>	
<p>DOI to processing steps BPMN</p>	
<p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15350707</p>	
<p>Additional remarks</p>	
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